

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Fault Resilience Analysis on Custom Fault Tolerant Interleaved Multi Threading processors (FRA_IMT)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-328
General application	<i>Space, high-reliability ground level</i>
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Marcello Barbirotta, Sapienza University of Rome</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	06/09/2024
Facility	<i>Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) Proton Facility</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	8

Objectives of the experiments

This proposal fits the vast scenario of microprocessor devices for FT COTS embedded applications, having as its basis the first detailed exploitation of the Interleave Multi-Threading (IMT) execution scheme for implementing fault tolerant processors on FPGA. It proposes a hardware fault injection (FI) campaign on new FT IMT architectures that implements new FT techniques correlated with simulation FI and power consumption results, which are useful for making direct comparisons.

The impact and potential of this work fill a gap in the literature by analyzing the FT potential of IMT architectures from the physical FI perspective, which is not covered by previous works in the field.

- It verifies the implementation of a new technique that merges spatial and temporal redundancy, referred to as Buffered TMR. Writing the three registers at different times, with the values from the corresponding thread, proves the advantage that an error in the combinational logic cannot be passed to more than one register at the same time, which decreases the probability that an error is passed among the different areas of the core, improving the reliability.
- It quantifies the effectiveness of the proposed technique using an extensive FI campaign under radiation facilities, showing that the achievable resilience can be comparable to a full TMR single-thread core, making the proposed technique well-suited for systems exposed to a relatively high fault rate or critical applications.
- It compares the approach with the unprotected architecture, opening the way to verifying other IMT FT approaches developed in the Klessydra core family and other FT techniques developed in the RISC-V context.

The general idea is to implement and test inside the FPGA, the basic version of the core (Klessydra-T03) and the FT version (Klessydra-fT03), proposing identical FI testing procedures to underscore their respective characteristics, differences, and enhancements in fault resilience. Subsequently, the

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results will be compared with the theoretical outcomes published in different works and derived from fault simulations.

The choice for proton testing was directed to the lack of literature, mostly dedicated to heavy ions or neutrons. Moreover, this was chosen to have a direct comparison with some works in the sector on RISC-V processors carried out with proton radiation.

Experiment test report

The tests were carried out on different FPGA boards named n°1,4,2 from the same FPGA family; Xilinx Artix7 on CMODA7 Digilent Board.

First, the beam was calibrated with the following parameters, choosing two energy ranges:

High energy = 200 MeV, fluence = 10^9 p/cm², and flux= 10^7 p/cm²/s

Medium energy = 50 MeV, fluence = 10^9 p/cm², and flux= 10^7 p/cm²/s

Second, we set up the environment by putting the DUT under the beam and connecting it to its control board, as shown in the image below.

After a few simple runs, the beam control software and the control board manually synchronized each test for the activation or deactivation of both the board and the beam, leading to data readback from the FPGA.

The 8 hours were divided into 6 different test campaigns, each with different runs for each design version (T03 and fT03), for a total duration of at least 100s per run. In particular were carried out:

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Test1 200MeV

5 runs for T03 -> Board n°1
 5 runs for fT03 -> Board n°1

Test2 200MeV

15 runs for T03 -> Board n°1
 15 runs for fT03 -> Board n°4

Test3 200MeV

10 runs for T03 -> Board n°4
 10 runs for fT03 -> Board n°4

Test4 50MeV

10 runs for T03 -> Board n°4
 10 runs for fT03 -> Board n°4

Test5 50MeV

3 runs for fT03 -> Board n°4

Test6 50MeV

8 runs for T03 -> Board n°2
 11 runs for fT03 -> Board n°2

At the beginning of each test, golden runs were carried out for direct comparison with subsequent faulted runs. Moreover, before and after each run, bitstream readback was performed for bit comparison and error checkout.

The final 95 collected tests will be subjected to post-processing analysis and cataloguing of the results.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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